

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8128463>

УДК 616-006.04

ANALYSIS OF CURRENT TRENDS IN THE INCIDENCE OF LUNG CANCER IN THE POPULATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS

T.I. Zimatkina,

Ph.D., Assoc.

A.S. Aleksandrovich,

Ph.D., Assoc.

A.S. Hramec,

Grodno state medical university

Grodno

Annotation: The current trends in the incidence of malignant lung tumors in the Republic of Belarus have been studied and analyzed. The materials for the study were the data of the state statistical reporting of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Belarus. Based on the analysis of the data, conclusions are drawn that positive trends are observed with respect to the dynamics of lung cancer incidence. There is a decrease in the number of cases of lung cancer among men and an increase in the incidence rate among women. An increase in morbidity was found in territories with unfavorable environmental conditions.

Keywords: morbidity, malignant tumors, lung cancer, trends, environmental situation

Relevance. Lung cancer is a complex concept. Cancer of this localization is the main cause of death of the population not only in the Republic of Belarus, but throughout the world. In 2020, this type of cancer not only took a leading position in the structure of oncological morbidity, but was also recognized as the main cause of death from malignant neoplasms among the world's population [1, 2].

Atmospheric air pollution, widespread acute and chronic bronchopulmonary pathology, repeated intensive chest irradiation, poor nutrition, exposure to toxic substances: radon, arsenic, benzopyrene,

asbestos – all these are predisposing factors to the development of lung cancer [3, 4]. However, the main risk factor was and remains tobacco smoking. Such a destructive habit turns out to be the main cause of cancer in 80 % of detected cases [5, 6].

The purpose of the study. To study and analyze the current trends in the incidence of malignant lung tumors in the Republic of Belarus in the period from 2010 to 2019.

Research methods. In this work, search, analytical, statistical, and epidemiological research methods were used. The materials for the study were the data of the state statistical reporting of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Belarus [7, 8].

The results of the study and their discussion. In the country for the period from 2010 to 2019, an increase in the incidence rate was registered in the class «Malignant neoplasms»: 459.1 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 484.3 – in 2014, 572.6 – in 2019, i.e. the increase compared to 2010 was 5.49 % and 24.72 %, respectively. In the structure of the main localizations, lung cancer occupies a leading position, while in the interval between 2010 (47.2 cases per 100 thousand population) and 2014 (46.1 cases per 100 thousand population), there has been a drop in the incidence of the aforementioned pathology by 2.39 % over the years. In 2019, a slight increase in morbidity was detected: 46.9 per 100 thousand population (an increase of 1.54 %). The morbidity of the able-bodied population was: 25.1 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 25.4 – in 2014, 26.4 – in 2019, which indicates an increase in morbidity by 5.21 % compared to 2010.

The percentage of cases of lung cancer in the structure of major oncological diseases in men is decreasing: 18.1 % – in 2010, 16.4 % – in 2014, 14.0 % – in 2019. The opposite trend is observed among women: 2.5 % – in 2010, 2.7 % – in 2014, 2.8 % – in 2019. A similar situation is observed in the category of the able-bodied population. For men, 19.8 % – in 2010, 17.4 % – in 2014, 14.6 % – in 2019 (a significant drop in morbidity by 5.2 %). In the structure of the morbidity of women over the last decade, a stable increase is visible: 1.5 % in 2010, 1.8 % in 2014, 2.0 % in 2019.

The urban population is characterized by an increase in the incidence of malignant tumors: 39.4 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 40.5 – in 2014 (an increase of 2.79 %), 41.1 – in 2019. (growth of

1.48 %). In the category of able-bodied citizens of the urban population, an increase in the number of patients with malignant lung tumors is also visible. From 2010 (20.2 cases per 100 thousand population) to 2014 (21.8 cases per 100 thousand population), the increase in the incidence rate was 7.9 %, in 2019 (22.4 cases per 100 thousand population) the resulting increase was 2.75 %. The reverse situation is typical for the rural population: 70.3 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 68.2 – in 2014, 65.0 – in 2019. Thus, we see a decrease in the number of detected cases between 2010 and 2014 – 3.07 % and between 2014 and 2019 – 4.92 %. Nevertheless, in the category of able-bodied citizens of the rural population, there is an increase in the incidence rate: 42.3 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 43.6 – in 2014 (an increase of 3.07 %), while in 2019 (48.9 cases per 100 thousand population) a significant increase in the incidence of 12.15 % was recorded.

Excellent trends in the dynamics of lung cancer incidence have been recorded in the regions of the Republic of Belarus. In the Brest region, there is a tendency to decrease the incidence rate: 46.8 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 43.9 – in 2014, 44.5 – in 2019. A similar situation is observed in the Grodno region: 44.4 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 40.4 – in 2014, 40.2 – in 2019. In the Gomel and Mogilev regions, as well as in the city of Minsk, there is a steady increase in the incidence rate. In Gomel 52.8 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 55.2 – in 2014. (growth of 4.54 %), 60.5 – in 2019. (growth of 9.6 %), in the Mogilev region 46.0 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 50.4 – in 2014 (growth of 9.56 %), 50.6 – in 2019. (growth of 0.39 %), and in the city of Minsk itself: 34.9 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 35.8 – in 2014 (growth of 2.57 %), 37.0 – in 2019. (growth of 3.35 %). Based on the data provided, the most significant increase in the incidence rate was detected in the Gomel region between 2014 and 2019, amounting to 9.6 %. in the Vitebsk and Minsk regions in the period 2010 – 2014. there is a decrease in the number of detected cases, and then in the period 2014-2019 the opposite trend: 55.9 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 55.6 – in 2014 (a drop in the incidence of 0.54 %), 60.5 – in 2019. (growth of 8.81 %). In Minsk, 53.5 cases per 100 thousand population in 2010, 47.4 – in 2014 (a drop in the incidence of 12.86 %), 48.9 – in 2019. (3.16 % growth). The average age of patients is gradually increasing, it was 63.0

years for 2010, 64.2 years for 2014 (an increase of 1.91 %), and 65.1 years for 2019 (an increase of 1.54 %).

Conclusions. Based on the analysis of the data, it was concluded that despite the increase in the number of registered cases of malignant formations, positive trends are observed with respect to the dynamics of the incidence of lung cancer.

There is a decrease in the number of cases of lung cancer among men, but an increase in the incidence rate among women, which is apparently due to the widespread use of tobacco smoking in this category of the population over the past decades.

An increase in morbidity was found in territories with unfavorable environmental conditions. In addition, the dependence of the prevalence of malignant lung tumors on the environmental situation can be traced in relation to the urban population.

Bibliography

[1] Cancer / WHO Newsletter. – 2021. [Electronic resource] – URL: <https://www.who.int/ru/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cancer>. (date of access: 02/25/2023).

[2] Radiobiology: medical and ecological problems: monograph / S.A. Maskevich, A.N. Batyan, T.I. Zimatkina [et al.] ; edited by prof. S. A. Maskevich ; International State Ecologist. in-t named after A. D. Sakharov Belarusian. state University; Grodno. state. med. un-T. – Minsk: IVC of the Ministry of Finance, 2019. 256 p.

[3] Oncological diseases of Belarus: premature mortality and social consequences / N.N. Antonenkova [et al.] // Oncological Journal. – 2012. Vol. 6, No. 1. 36-44 p.

[4] Official website of the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Belarus [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://www.belstat.gov.by/>. – Access date: 02/25/2023.

[5] Zimatkina T.I. Ecological medicine: a workshop for students studying in the specialties 1-79 01 01 «Medical business», 1-79 01 02 «Pediatrics» / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich, G. D. Smirnova. – Grodno: GrSMU, 2021. 238 p.

[6] Zimatkina T.I. Modern trends in morbidity and mortality of the Republic of Belarus in connection with malignant neoplasms of different

localization / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich // Radiation and environmental medicine: modern problems, a look into the future: collection of materials of the Rep. scientific-practical conference with international participation, Grodno, September 29-30, 2022 – Grodno, 2022. 124-130 p.

[7] Aleksandrovich A.S. Analysis of morbidity and mortality of the population of the Republic of Belarus with malignant neoplasms / A.S. Aleksandrovich, T.I. Zimatkina // Modern issues of radiation and environmental medicine, radiation diagnostics and therapy: collection of materials of the Republican Scientific and Practical Conference with international participation, September 23-24, 2021 – Grodno, 2021. 16-21 p.

[8] Zimatkina T.I. Some aspects of the modern radiation-ecological situation in the Republic of Belarus / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich, D.V. Mironyuk, E. I. Vasilevich // Modern problems of radiation medicine: from science to practice: materials of the International scientific-practical conference, Gomel, June 19, 2020 – Gomel, 2020. 35-37 p.

© T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich, A.S. Hramec, 2023

Поступила в редакцию 12.06.2023

Принята к публикации 15.06.2023

Для цитирования:

Zimatkina T.I., Aleksandrovich A.S., Hramec A.S. Analysis of current trends in the incidence of lung cancer in the population of the Republic of Belarus // Инновационные научные исследования. 2023. № 6-3(30). С. 65-69. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>